

CHEMICAL PRODUCT DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT: LEARNING FROM STUDENT EXPERIENCE

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Abstract

The Diploma in Chemical Engineering at Singapore Polytechnic had adopted the CDIO (conceive, design, implement, operate) framework for its teachings and had introduced chemical product design into its curriculum. CDIO framework is a model for education reform that many educational institutions around the globe had adopted to reform their programs. Chemical product design is an emerging trend in the education of chemical engineers, namely that in applying a set of chemical engineering principles to the design of a product using a simplified 4-step systematic approach already used in the business world: (1) Needs, (2) Ideas, (3) Selection, and (4) Manufacture.

This paper details our effort to integrate chemical product design into our 3-year program as fulfilment of the CDIO requirements. It firstly explains the current teaching and its shortcomings, and briefly introduces the relevant CDIO requirements. It then presents details of the new *Product Design and Development* module, including the module aims, topics covered and assessment schemes. It next discusses the experience gained from conducting a student survey about their learning experience in the module. Lastly, it presents action plans that we will take to improve the teachings of the module.

Keywords: *chemical product design, CDIO, chemical engineering*

Introduction: Shortcomings of Present Teaching

Chemical product design is a relatively new topic in the education of chemical engineers (Costa, et al 2006). It had recently gained importance due to increased globalization, sustainability concerns and advances in technology such as nanotechnology and green engineering. In the chemical industry, there had been a fundamental shift from production of bulk (commodity) chemicals to specialty chemicals with specific user-defined functions, varying greatly from drugs, additives, coatings, etc. Chemical engineering graduates are now wanted in industries that did not exist 10 - 20 years ago or did not until recently discover the usefulness and relevance of chemical engineers in their profession (Prausnitz, 2001). Today, most organizations fill their

knowledge gaps by utilizing cross-functional decision-making teams. And the way chemical engineers worked has also changed fundamentally. In essence, to be an engineer means being involved in customer satisfaction, applied research, product development, process and manufacturing controls, and marketing (Stevens, 2003).

Over the last couple of years, universities around the world had added chemical product design into their curriculum. We at the Diploma in Chemical Engineering in Singapore Polytechnic also recognised the growing importance of chemical product design and had taken steps to equip our students with skills in this area.

We developed a 75-hr module entitled *Product Design and Development (PDD)* to be taught to Year 2 students, over 2 semesters, totalling 30 weeks. This module is introduced to supplement a Year 1 institutional module entitled *Innovation Design and Enterprise in Action (IDEA)*. In our context, an institutional module is a module with standard curriculum prescribed to all students in Singapore Polytechnic, i.e. it is a compulsory study regardless of what diploma program they are enrolled into. The rationale of having institutional modules is to ensure that every full-time SP graduate has attained a minimum level of skill or ability in certain competencies deemed important by the institution.

In the case of *IDEA*, it is a 30-hr module with a fixed curriculum, whose main objective is to develop in students an attitude for basic creativity, design literacy, innovation and enterprise, through an understanding of the design process. Through experiential project-based learning, students are required to question their preconceptions, see things from multiple perspectives, generate new ideas and make them work, develop visual and verbal presentation to sell their new ideas to others to create new uses and lifestyles.

However, our students often failed to appreciate the teachings of the *IDEA* module, as the fixed curriculum is viewed as rather remote from their study in chemical engineering. Concepts such as ethnography (observation and analysis of consumer behaviors to identify desired experiences) and designing consumer touch points (to deliver desired consumption experiences) proved too abstract to our students who are more acquainted to the

systematic problem-solving approach of engineering education. As a result, there is often a “disconnection” between *IDEA* and Year 3 *Final Year Project (FYP)*, where students often unable to apply the concepts taught in *IDEA* to their work in *FYP*.

CDIO and Chemical Product Design

To bridge the gap between *IDEA* and *FYP*, we leveraged on the CDIO framework that we adopted as the basis of revamping our chemical engineering curriculum (Cheah, 2008). CDIO Standard 5 “Design-Build Experiences” prescribed “a curriculum that includes two or more design-build experiences (DBE), including one at a basic level and one at an advanced level”. In the CDIO context, the term *design-build experience* denotes “a range of engineering activities central to the process of developing new products and systems. Included are all of the activities described in Standard One at the *Design* and *Implement* stages, plus appropriate aspects of conceptual design from the *Conceive* stage. Students develop product and system building skills, as well as the ability to apply engineering science, in design-build experiences integrated into the curriculum. Design-build experiences are considered *basic* or *advanced* in terms of their scope, complexity, and sequence in the program. For example, simpler products and systems are included earlier in the program, while more complex design-build experiences appear in later courses designed to help students integrate knowledge and skills acquired in preceding courses and learning activities”.

CDIO Standard 5 further noted that “design-build experiences are structured and sequenced to promote early success in engineering practice. Iteration of design-build experiences and increasing levels of design complexity reinforce students’ understanding of the product and system development process. Design-build experiences also provide a solid foundation upon which to build deeper conceptual understanding of disciplinary skills. The emphasis on building products and implementing processes in real-world contexts gives students opportunities to make connections between the technical content they are learning and their professional and career interests”.

Product Design and Development for the Diploma in Chemical Engineering

The aims of the *PDD* module is to inculcate in students the necessary skills in conceiving, designing, implementing, and operating an engineering product or system using chemical engineering principles. This will culminate in a more effective execution of the students’ *FYP*, i.e. the so-called capstone project in CDIO parlance.

The introduction of this new module is achieved through changes in course structure where we streamlined a number of core chemical engineering modules by merging overlapping modules as well as

removing obsolete modules. The design of the *PDD* curriculum, including both teaching and assessment, draws on the Top 10 Recommendations as outlined by Edstrom et al (2003), who derived them based on their work on student learning experience:

1. Set clear objectives that are relevant to the engineer: “After this course you will be able to...”
2. Design assessment tasks and teaching that are relevant to the objectives.
3. Focus on working knowledge of basic concepts and provide connections to reality. Application is the road to understanding theory.
4. Prioritize - Remember: coverage is the enemy of understanding.
5. Set an assessment task early in the course.
6. Set assessment tasks regularly during the course.
7. Produce explicit criteria for assessment. Make sure students know exactly what is expected of them.
8. Design tasks and activities with built-in interaction.
9. Make a realistic plan for the time the students spend on the course. Coordinate deadlines and workload with parallel courses.
10. Show with your enthusiasm that the course and its tasks are worth doing.

The students were informed at the first lecture the following module aims:

“At the end of the module, students will be able to:

1. Identify and translate customer needs into preliminary product design specifications.
2. Use a range of creative thinking tools and techniques
3. Evaluate an idea
4. Use system thinking in problem solving
5. Apply technical knowledge learnt to create a prototype

The idea selected in this module can be further refined and lead to the conception of a suitable product for subsequent design, implementation and operation.”

The content of the *PDD* module was derived largely from the 4-step process first proposed by Cussler and Moggridge (2001). In a nutshell, the procedure centered around the concepts of “needs”, “ideas”, “selection”, and “manufacture’ as follows:

1. Needs: What needs should the product fill?
2. Ideas: What different products could fill this need?
3. Selection: Which ideas are the most promising?
4. Manufacture: How can we make the product and test it critically?

We added in other contents that are relevant to meeting our own needs such as the teaching of good thinking skills (e.g. critical thinking, creative thinking and systems thinking), as well as intellectual property rights and project execution. The module was introduced to the students for the first time in April 2009. Table 1 showed the broad topics covered in this 75-hour module.

Table 1
Topics covered in *PDD*

A	INTRODUCTION TO CHEMICAL PRODUCT DESIGN (4 Hours)
1	Understand Chemical Product Design
B	NEED ANALYSIS (8 Hours)
2	Identify and translate customer needs
C	IDEA GENERATION (24 Hours)
3	Critical thinking and creative thinking
4	Use idea creation techniques.
D	SCREENING AND SELECTION OF IDEAS AND SOLUTIONS (20 Hours)
5	Select ideas for further implementation
E	SYSTEMS THINKING (6 Hours)
6	Apply systems thinking to product design
F	MANUFACTURE AND MARKETING OF PRODUCT (13 Hours)
7	Understand the intellectual property issues in product manufacture
8	Understand the requirement for project execution

The *PDD* module also serves to reinforce the two DBEs introduced earlier: one basic-level DBE in Year 1 *Introduction to Chemical Engineering*, and another intermediate-level DBE in Year 2 *Chemical Reaction Engineering* which were both rolled out in April 2008 as part of the launch of CDIO-enabled chemical engineering curriculum. Briefly stated, the DBE in *Introduction to Chemical Engineering* serves to introduce students to project work early in their course of study where they are required to build – without engineering design – a simple water filter with prescribed materials; while the DBE in *Chemical Reaction Engineering* serves to reinforce project work experience by requiring students to design, by doing some basic calculations, and build a simple chemical reactor. In both projects the students are required to evaluate the performance of their devices. Student feedback regarding their learning experiences in these modules had been positive and already covered in past papers (Cheah, 2009; Yang and Cheah, 2009).

The *PDD* module is assessed fully based on in-course continuous assessments, as shown in Table 2. In addition to the formal assessments of Table 2, we included various interactive classroom activities to regularly engage the students in various discussions, for example, design of survey questionnaire, patent search,

visit a company renowned for product innovation, talks on innovation fund, etc. Comprehensive assessment criteria were also developed, as shown in Appendix 1.

Table 2
Assessment Scheme for *PDD*

Continuous Assessment	Means of Assessment	Weighting (%)
Product Design Assessment No. 1 – User Research	Mini Research Report	15
	Oral Presentation	15
Product Design Assessment 2 – Design and Development of a Prototype	Final Project Report	40
	Logbook	10
	Oral Presentation	20

At the point of this writing, we have completed a pilot year of teaching of *Product Design and Development*. A total of 60 projects from 20 groups were proposed in this module, where some of the more interesting ones are listed in Table 3 below:

Table 3
List of projects proposed by students from *PDD*

Eco Dance Floor	Color coating for Lenses
Self-cleaning table	Massager backpack
Blue corn milk	Sweat-to-ester deodorant
Detergent stick	Waterproof spray plaster
Magical white board	Ash-less incense paper
Fluorescent umbrella	Anti-smoking perfume
Scented medicated oil	Exotic fragrance shower gel
Free-form earpiece	Generator bike
Water cum fertilizer sprinkler	

Students interested in furthering their work from the *PDD* module into Year 3 *FYP* can submit their proposals for student-initiated projects and source for suitable lecturers to be their supervisors.

Module Evaluation: Results and Discussions of Learning Points

We surveyed the students for their learning experience of this module. A combination of methods was used. To gauge student receptiveness of the module and general awareness about the fundamental differences between chemical product design and more ‘traditional’ chemical process design, we used a 5-point Likert scale. Students are asked to indicate their feeling, ranging from ‘1’ for Strongly Disagree to ‘5’ for Strongly Agree. For more specific questions such as using creative thinking skills and challenges faced, the checklist method is used, followed by open-ended questions. The evaluation results can be discussed under several themes:

Students Perception of the Module

For the statement “*I find this module rather interesting as it offers something different from other modules in the Diploma in Chemical Engineering*”, student responses are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overall Perception of Module

For the statement “*Overall, I am aware of a different dimension in chemical engineering: that I can apply its principles to product design and development, other than process simulation and plant design*”, student responses are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Overall Awareness of New Dimension in Chemical Engineering

For the statement “*As a result of taking this module, I have gained the knowledge and skills conceiving and proposing an engineering solution for a chemical product to meet the needs of customers*”, student responses are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. New Skill Gained

Analyzed together, these figures showed that while students in general have high awareness of a new dimension in chemical engineering in the form of product design (Figure 2), overall many are still unsure about the usefulness of the module (Figures 1 and 3). A large number of them remained neutral about studying the module (41.0%, Figure 1), as the way it was taught was rather different from other more “traditional” core chemical engineering modules. And although an equally large number of students (40.8%, Figure 3) reported Neutral on learning new skills, there is also a large percentage (51.0%) that agreed that they had learnt useful skills.

We also probed the students’ understanding of Intellectual Property Rights, by presenting them the following statement “*I understand the importance of IPR (Intellectual Property Rights) in product manufacture*”. The student responses are shown in Figure 4. In this area, students reported high agreement overall (more than 75%). We believe this can be attributed to the special lecture delivered by an external guest on the topic.

Figure 4. Awareness of IPR

Students’ Ability to Use Specific Skills in the Module

To obtain more in-depth understanding of the various thinking tools preferred by students, out of the many that were taught to them, we use checklist coupled with open-ended questions.

For use of critical thinking techniques, the following statement was given:

I am able to use the following critical thinking techniques in generating product ideas - Tick (✓) all boxes that are applicable:

- Six Thinking Hats
- PMI (Plus-Minus-Interesting)
- Force Field Analysis
- Mind Map
- Others - Please specify: _____

As can be seen from the results in Figure 5, the majority of students used mind maps. A limited number of students quoted fish bone diagram and mix-

and-match. We also noted that students have the tendency to use only one method, or at most two methods. Only 9 students (or 9.3%) used three or more methods.

Figure 5. Use of Critical Thinking Techniques

To assess students' ability to use the various techniques to evaluate their ideas, they were asked to rate the statement "I am able to apply the techniques of sorting and screening ideas that I was taught". The responses as shown in Figure 6 indicated that while many (over 40%) agreed or strongly agreed that they can use the techniques, there are still half the students who remained uncertain in this regards. This showed that while slightly more than half of them acknowledged that they are aware of such skills (Figure 3 previously), many still lacked confidence in utilizing these skills.

Figure 6. Idea Sorting and Screening Techniques

For use of creative thinking techniques, the following statement was given:

I am able to use the following creative thinking techniques in generating product ideas - Tick (✓) all boxes that are applicable:

- SCAMPER
- Brainstorming
- Provocation (through Thought Experiments)
- TRIZ
- Metaphor
- Others - Please specify: _____

From the results in Figure 7, we see that the most popular methods are Brainstorming and SCAMPER respectively. Similarly, most students have the tendency to use only one or at most two methods. Only 16 (or 16.5%) used three or more methods. A somewhat surprise finding is the use of TRIZ as reported by up to 35% of the students. Perhaps not surprisingly, students in general are uncomfortable with more "abstract" methods such as metaphor and thought experiments.

Figure 7. Use of Creative Thinking Techniques

Challenges Faced by Students

In the next part of the survey, we queried the students on the challenges faced when studying the module. Specifically, we asked:

What are some of the challenges you faced in the study of this module? Tick (✓) 2 boxes that are most significant:

- Designing survey questionnaire
- Using critical and/or creative thinking skills
- Lacking knowledge in relevant chemical engineering principles appropriate for my proposal
- Working within my group to screen and select the best idea for implementation
- Taking initiative to sound out different lecturers about your ideas
- Others - Please specify: _____

What we found, in order of decreasing difficulty, is as follows:

- Lack of chemical engineering knowledge (64 students)
- Critical or creative thinking (45 students)
- Taking initiative to sound out lecturers (25 students)
- Team agreement of idea selection (19 students)
- Designing questionnaire (17 students)
- Others: 5 students cited "No time", 1 cited "Creating prototype", 1 cited "Business proposal"

This paper focused on discussing the first three issues. The first challenge is not entirely surprising. The students had not mastered all the various chemical engineering principles in Year 2. This is especially the case when they are in Semester 1 of Year 2, when they only began to learn about various chemical engineering principles such as fluid mechanics and heat transfer mechanisms. A survey of the various core chemical engineering modules also revealed the lack of worked examples in the area of chemical product design. The various tutorials in the core modules are provided to, firstly demonstrate the application of various engineering formula, and secondly in the design of process equipment such as pumps, heat exchangers, and separation columns.

The lack of suitable examples on chemical product design also diminished students' ability to think creatively and/or critically. Kazerounian and Foley (2007) asserted that creativity is possible for engineering students and had identified some barriers to creativity. Among these are: uncomfortable with ambiguity over the outcome, inability to keep an open mind when viewing a problem; and lack of inducement for creative behaviour, whether real or perceived. Although not explicitly mentioned by students in the survey, we believe these are some of the contributing factors.

On the issues of students approaching lecturers for advice, many reported that they are not aware of each lecturer's respective area of expertise, as they had not been taught by the lecturer. Hence they are rather apprehensive in approaching any lecturer out of fear of being turned away. Some students may also have some (often unjustified) preconceived notion about the "relative approachability" of various lecturers.

On the other hand, we believed that another unarticulated factor is the lack of product design skills among the lecturer themselves. The above-mentioned barriers to creativity apply equally well to lecturers as well. Except for a handful of lecturers who are involved in the teaching of *IDEA* and *PDD*, the rest are trained in the "traditional" chemical engineering that focuses on process design rather than product design. Although basic training in chemical product design had been conducted, it is a fact that these lecturers lacked real-world experience in this area; and thus are uncomfortable in dealing with the uncertain outcomes inherent in product design and development.

Students' Perception of Extending *PDD* into *FYP*

Lastly, we would like to know the students anticipation on continuing what they had done in the *PDD* module into Year 3 *FYP*. The following question was asked:

Which of the descriptions below best describe your feeling towards executing a Final Year Project based on your own idea? Tick (✓) ONE box only:

- Rejection – I'd rather do a project prescribed by the lecturer
- Indifferent – I am fine with either lecturer-prescribed project or my own project
- Mixed – Although I do look forward to carrying out my own project, I am somewhat worried if I can achieve what I set out to do
- Excited – I can't wait to realize my dream of doing my own project, regardless of the outcome whether I am successful or not
- Others - Please specify: _____

Figure 8. Attitude toward continuing *PDD* as *FYP*

As can be seen in Figure 8, many students (up to 51%) are rather apprehensive when it comes to continuing their work in *PDD* as their *FYP*. The reasons offered by students for expressing Rejection, Indifferent or Mixed feelings in their responses, are as follows in order of frequency of occurrence:

- Concern over workability of idea or concept proposed in *PDD*
- Lack of or no confidence that one is able to succeed
- Insufficient technical knowledge
- Play safe – own ideas not very good or too complicated, easier to focus if lecturer provide project
- Concern over outcome affecting cumulative GPA (Grade Point Average)
- *PDD* proposal lacked chemical engineering component
- View lecturer-proposed project as back-up in case *PDD* proposal fails
- Incompatible interest among group members
- Not enough time to explore further the idea in *PDD*

The predominant view among students from the above is clear. As many had cited insufficient understanding of applicable chemical engineering principles as the main challenge faced, it is therefore not surprising that students generally are reluctant to carry forward the work done in *PDD* as their *FYP*. Students in general are also unsure what sort of experimentation work that can be carried out on the *PDD* proposal to link it to *FYP*. For example, a group may be interested in producing scented medicated oil,

but was unsure the kind of experimentation required for product realization. Students also lacked skills in basic experiments such as organic synthesis and formulation. Although they had been encouraged to seek out lecturers to help them in defining the scope for possible *FYP*, many are reluctant to do so, for the reasons outlined previously. Many students are also under the wrong impression that they need to produce a physical prototype, or even a working model! Some expressed concern over the consequence of a “poor” proposal on their overall grades.

Notwithstanding the above, we noted that many groups went beyond what is required of them from the course assessment point of view. From some of the assignment, we see that students applied some knowledge not explicitly taught in the *PDD* module, or in other core chemical engineering modules. Some included discussion of UPS (unique selling point), financials (balance sheet, profit & loss statement), factory location, SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats) analysis, possible competitor response, future expansion plans, and bankruptcy.

Of those students who went ahead nonetheless, some of the reasons cited as their main motivating factor are: “chance to carry out something that they actually interested in”, “need not be subjected to balloting process, in case we got project that we do not liked”, “we want to be the one deciding what we wanted to do”. Of the 20 “finalist” proposals from *PDD*, 2 were continued as *FYP*.

Future Plans

First and foremost, we will have to better manage the students’ expectations right at the beginning of the module. We need to have a clearer assessment scheme that emphasizes the “process outcome” rather than the “product outcome”. Here what we meant is the assessment of students’ ability to use the various skills (such as ideation, idea selection, solution formulation and selection); and not the workability of the prototype or “final” product. This will be highlighted at regular intervals over the entire two semesters. With this, we will be able to encourage more creative thinking and risk taking.

We acknowledged that “delays” in knowledge acquisition is an inevitable outcome of a modular way of teaching. To address this, we would emphasize greater independent learning on the part of the students, to pick up new concepts that are not yet taught in class. The student module registration process will need to be reviewed. Currently students can only view the online course materials of the modules for which they are registered, i.e. Year 2 students in Semester 1 are unable to access materials for Year 2 Semester 2, or for that matter any semesters of Year 1 and Year 3. This is necessary to supplement the resources available in the library, as all chemical engineering textbooks are pegged at university

teaching, which is of higher level than diploma. By making more in-house resources available to students any time, we make it easier for students to acquire the necessary knowledge needed for their *PDD* proposals.

To reinforce the above, we also hope to introduce more examples on application of various chemical engineering principles such as fluid mechanics, heat transfer, etc in product design and development. This can be achieved by having more tutorial questions on chemical product design embedded in the relevant core chemical engineering modules. Promoting such greater curriculum integration can also help students better understand the connections between different chemical engineering concepts and principles taught in separate modules. The challenge is to source for sufficient examples of chemical product design suitable for use at the diploma level.

To encourage more creative behaviour and risk taking among students, we plan to introduce more success stories into the teaching. This approach, coupled with clear learning outcome that emphasize the utilization of creative and critical thinking skills, will serve to allay students’ fear of being penalized for “poor” products.

We are now in the process of studying the possibility of introducing various experiments on basic chemical engineering sciences such as mixing, colloid formation, surface tension measurement, viscosity modification, etc. This will be a calculated move away from pilot plant operations which is the traditional training our students received. This will provide students with hands-on experience in conducting experimental work for their proposed chemical products. We are in the process of identifying suitable experiments. However, adding on more experiments to an already-packed curriculum may pose a challenge.

We will also review if longer timeline need to be provided for students to seek out suitable lecturers to become their *FYP* supervisors. Currently, students completed their *PDD* assignment near the end of Semester 2 of Year 2. There are about eight weeks (comprising of two weeks of examination and six weeks of vacation) before the beginning of Year 3 where students start their *FYP*. For various administrative reasons (including funding request and allocation), all *FYP* proposals must be finalized at least four weeks before the starts of Year 3. That leaves very little time for students to search for supervisors, who will be busy with examination matters at that time. See Figure 9. Under the proposed system, the schedule for oral presentation can be shifted forward, leaving some room for class lecturers at the end of the semester before the examination week. We can also reduce by one week the preparation time before the roll-out of *FYP* on the following academic year. This allows more time for students to scout for suitable lecturers as their *FYP* supervisors.

And lastly, though not the least important, is the training of lecturers. More lecturers need to be exposed to real-world chemical product design work, and we propose this be achieved via industrial attachment to relevant companies such as Philips (at their Philips Innovation Campus) or 3M. This will also help to encourage more buy-in to overcome the problem of lack of confidence on the part of many lecturers, as identified above.

Acad Calendar	Yr 2 Sem 2 (15 wks)						Exam (2 wks)		Semester Vacation (6 wks)						Yr 3 Sem 1 (15 wks)	
	Week No	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	01
Current System	Classes as Usual		Oral Presentation			Report	Sourcing for Supervisor			Preparing for FYP			Roll-out FYP			
Proposed System	Oral Presentation		Class. Report,			Sourcing for Supervisor			Preparing for FYP			Roll-out FYP				

Figure 9. Current and Proposed Timeline for Transition from PDD to FYP

Conclusions

The new module *Product Design and Development* had been introduced to Year 2 students from the Diploma in Chemical Engineering as a pilot run in April 2009. While the module served its intended function of bridging the gap between Year 1 teaching and Year 3 project work, there are several problems that were identified from survey of the students' learning experience. The main lesson learnt is for both lecturers and students to overcome the barriers to creative thinking and move away from the mindset of diving straight into offering preconceived solutions instead of exploring other possible alternative, equally viable but more attractive solutions.

For the program to be successful, efforts are required from both lecturers and students. The lecturers need to be further trained in chemical product design, and students need to be provided with more resources to enable them to cope with the demand of the module. Action plans had been formulated and some of these had been implemented at the time of this paper.

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Appendix 1 Assessment Criteria

Product Design Assessment No.1 (User Research)

In this team assignment, you are required to observe and find out from your daily lives bug lists of problems that you have to face everyday which are preferably chemical in nature, and come up with some innovative solutions to the top three short-listed problems. You can also revisit the laboratories and practical workshops where you had attended and are attending and identify the problems you observed. You must be able to identify the product/design attributes on how they solve your stipulated problem, and enhancements needed to satisfy the functional (and marketing, if any) requirements. The examples of chemical and chemical related industries you may want to explore include, but are not limited, to the following areas.

Biochemical	Petroleum & Oil
Biotechnology	Refining
(Biomedical & Healthcare)	Pharmaceuticals
Chemicals	Plastics & Polymers
Cosmetics	Process Control & Instrumentation
Environment and Energy	Process Engineering
Fertilizers	Semiconductors & Electronics
Food and Beverages	Ultra-pure Water
Energy & Fuels	Wastewater Treatment
Petrochemicals	Specialty Chemicals

To do this assignment, you will have to:

- identify the bugs or problems in the daily lives or in the laboratories / workshops / industries which are preferably chemical in nature
- analyze the customer needs in these problems via end-user surveys and questionnaires
- analyze the chemical and design components of a product
- apply the creative problem solving process to generate new products
- produce design specifications of possible new products for the industry

Product Design Assessment No.2 (Design and Development of a Prototype)

To do this assignment, you will have to:

- refine the solution you proposed earlier based on your latest research, technical and fundamental knowledge, feedback and comments from your classmates and lecturers during the Question and Answer session in Assessment No.1
- propose appropriate marketing strategies
- create a prototype using low cost materials

Mini Research Report (marks allocation in brackets)

1. Effective identification / interpretation of customer needs (20%)
 - Effective use of a range of critical thinking skills (e.g. analysis, comparison and contrast, inference and interpretation, evaluation)
 - Effective identification of opportunities/problems via market-research surveys, end-user surveys, questionnaires etc to collate feedback
 - Conversion of the customer needs to initial specifications qualitatively/quantitatively
2. Technical knowledge and reasoning applied in problem solving (20%)
 - Effective use of domain knowledge and technical facts in proposed solution
 - Research or literature survey conducted on the specific problem and proposed solution
3. Creativity and innovation in problem solving (20%)
 - Effective use of a range of critical thinking skills (e.g. analysis, comparison and contrast, inference and interpretation, evaluation)
 - Effective use of creative thinking tools and techniques
 - Identify contradictory perspectives and underlying assumptions
4. Teamwork (20%)
 - Effective identification of team roles after analyzing each member's strength and weakness
 - Good management of time and resources in the whole assignment
5. Preliminary Work (20%)
 - Carry out sufficient literature search to meet the scope of the project
 - Plan to organize work schedule logically and independently

Final Project Report (marks allocation in brackets)

1. Application of technical knowledge & reasoning to refine the solution (40%)
 - Able to address key issues raised from your classmates and lecturers
 - Apply the technical knowledge and reasoning to refine the design
 - Effective use of creative thinking tools and techniques
2. Effectiveness of marketing approach of the product (20%)
 - Analysis on how this product is different from the existing similar products in the market (if any)
 - Proposal on how to market this innovative product or possible avenue for enterprise
3. Creation of prototype (40%)
 - Effective use of design of experiments to identify the optimum specification of the product or prototype
 - Identification of opportunities for further work at the Final Year Project level

Oral Presentation

The work produced by the team should be presented as an organized presentation. The structure and presentation must clearly show the development of your thinking and acquisition of knowledge to the production of the initial design. You must include appropriate diagrams and products, e.g. models, to illustrate the important stages of the design process. It is essential that all members contribute to the presentation in approximately equal parts. The team will be expected to answer questions posed by assessing lecturers and your classmates.

1. Design and deliver presentation well in proper and formal English
2. Speak clearly and coherently
3. Ask and answer questions effectively
4. Exhibits technical competency and know-how in the project